

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on Knowledge Regarding ICDS Programme among Selected Mothers of Under-Five Children

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To knowledge regarding ICDS programme among mothers of under-five Children.

Methods Pre-experimental study was carried over a period of 3 on 30 mothers of under-five children in Ramanagar Village, Belagavi Karnataka. All 30 mothers enrolled in study.

Results: The study findings reveals that the overall pre test mean knowledge scores as 33.5% and the post test knowledge scores as 72.3%. The mean enhancement score was found to be 38.8%. The statistical results established significant at 5% level ($t=52.09^*$) indicating the effectiveness of structured teaching programme in enhancing the knowledge of respondents.

Conclusion: Structured Teaching Programme is the best methods to improve the knowledge on ICDS Programme among mothers of under-five children.

Keywords: Assess, Structure teaching programme, knowledge, Mothers of under-five children, ICDS Programme.

INTRODUCTION

India is the second most populated and the seventh largest country in the world. A special demographic feature of our country is that it has a sizeable proportion of young population. One-sixth of India's population falls in the 0-6 years age group. Thus children and young adults are dominant and this leads to an unfavourable

age structure with a large population of juvenile population.

In spite of all the developmental efforts and achievements of the successive 5 year plans, we are still not a healthy nation. The input mortality rate is still high in our country. An extremely high percentage of the child population suffers childhood diseases such as malnutrition, pneumonia, gastro-intestinal disorders, respiratory infections etc. A vast majority of pregnant and nursing mothers, especially belonging to the low socio-economic group live on diets which are inadequate. The percentage of drop outs from the school system is extremely high. Thus, it has become essential to promote the development of the ICDS scheme Children are the first call on agenda of human resource development – not only because young children are the most vulnerable, but because the foundation for lifelong learning and human development is laid in these crucial early years. It is now globally acknowledged that investment in human resources development is a pre-requisite for economic development of any nation. [1]

India is the home to the largest child population in the world. "The development of children is the first priority on the country's development agenda, not because they are the most vulnerable, but because they are our supreme assets and also the future human resources of the country". In

these words, our Tenth Five Year Plan (2002-07) underlines the fact that the future of India lies in the future of Indian children.

The first six years of a child's life are most crucial as the foundations for cognitive, social, emotional, physical, motor and psychological development are laid at this stage. . Child survival, growth and development, has to be looked at as a holistic approach, as one cannot be achieved without the others. There have to be balanced linkages between education, health and nutrition for proper development of a child.

As per Census of India 2001, there are 157.86 million children below six years of age, and many of them have inadequate access to health care, nutrition, sanitation, child care, early stimulation, etc. To ensure that all young children, even those from vulnerable sections of society have access to their basic rights, ICDS was launched in 1975 to provide a package of services to ensure their holistic development.

The objectives of ICDS are to improve the nutritional and health status of children in the age-group 0-6 years, to lay the foundation for proper psychological, physical and social development of the child, to reduce the incidence of mortality, morbidity, malnutrition and school dropout, to achieve effective co-ordination of policy and implementation amongst the various departments to promote child development; and to enhance the capability of the mother to look after the normal health and nutritional needs of the child through proper nutrition and health education.^[3]

Today, ICDS Scheme represents one of the world's largest and most unique programmes for early childhood development. ICDS is the foremost symbol of India's commitment to her children. ICDS provides services like supplementary nutrition, immunization, health check up, referral services, preschool non-formal education, and nutrition & health education to young children and their mothers. ICDS also empowers mothers to take better care of their children.^[1]

The ICDS program provides an integrated approach for converging all the basic services for improved childcare, early stimulation and learning, health and nutrition, water and environmental sanitation aimed at the young children, expectant and lactating mothers, other women and adolescent girls in a community. ICDS program is the reflection of the Government of India to effectively improve the nutrition and health status of underprivileged section of the population through direct intervention mechanism.^[4]

During the Eleventh Five Year Plan (2007-2012), nutritionally backward states would be the focus of special attention, and micronutrient supplementation/ fortification would be used as a strategy to combat specific micronutrient deficiencies. The involvement of Panchayats, women's self help groups (SHGs), NGOs, corporate and business houses, and other civil society organizations usher in public-private partnership in the true spirit of the concept.^[2]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was Pre-experimental study carried out at Ramanagar Village, Belagavi Karnataka for a period of 3 months. The study was approved by the institutional research committee.

The tool used for the data collection consisted of: The self administered structured questionnaire to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding ICDS Programme among mothers of under-five children at Ramanagar Village, Belagavi Karnataka.

Tool was divided into two parts section I & section II

Section I - Demographic data

Section II - Self administered structured questionnaire on ICDS Programme

RESEARCH DESIGN:

Pre- Experimental one group pretest posttest research design has been adopted for the present study.

RESULTS

Analysis of the data shows that majority of Plywood Industry workers in Pretest knowledge score was inadequate 86.66% (>50 %), Moderate 13.34% (<50 %) and Adequate was 0.0% (> 75 %).

But in post test 63.0% of them had moderate knowledge (51-75 %), 36.67% of them had adequate knowledge (< 50 %) and none of them had inadequate knowledge (\leq 50 %), which indicates that the Structured Teaching Programme improved the knowledge of mothers of under-five children regarding ICDS Programme.

Major Findings Of The Study were:

Descriptive and inferential statistics had been used for data analysis. The data was presented in the form of tables and diagrams. Data was analyzed by computing mean, standard deviation, t value and Chi - square test.

Significant Findings Of the Study Demographic Data Of The Respondent

Age:

Majority 60% were in the age group of 20-30 and 40% were 31-40 years.

Marital Status:

Maximum number of respondents 86.5 % we are married, and 10.0% widow.

Educational status:

50% of samples are studied 6-10thstd and 43.33% samples are studied 5-10thstd and 6.66% are PUC& above.

Religion:

Majority 66.66% of the respondents were belongs to Hindu religion and 33.33% from Muslim religion.

Type of family:

Majority of respondents 56.66 % belongs to nuclear family followed by 43.33 % of the respondents were from joint family.

Monthly Income:

The maximum number of respondents 83.33% were had monthly income below Rs. 15,000 and minimum number of respondents 13.33% had a family income between Rs. 20,000-25,000

Association between knowledge scores with selected demographic variables:

The present study was analysed the no significant association between pre test and post knowledge scores with demographic variables.

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation and t value regarding over all Pre test and Post test Knowledge on ICDS programme. N=30

Aspects	Max. Score	Respondents Knowledge				Paired 't' Test
		Mean	SD	Mean (%)	SD (%)	
Pre test	20	6.7	3.34	33.5%	16.7%	15.70*
Post test	20	14.46	2.53	72.3%	12.6%	
Enhancement	20	7.76	2.71	38.8%	13.5%	

Significant at 5% level, $t(0.05,29df) = 2.05$

The data presented shows that overall mean percentage of post-test knowledge score was 14.46(72.3%) with 2.53(12.6%) SD significantly higher than overall mean of pre-test knowledge score was 6.7(33.5%) with 3.34(16.7%) SD. There was an enhancement of 7.76(38.8%) mean with 2.71(13.5%) SD. 't' value computed between pre-test and post-test knowledge score is statistically significant ($t_{(Cal)} = 15.70$, table value $t_{(29)} = 2.05$, $p < 0.05$). The calculated 't' value was greater than table value. Hence research hypothesis was accepted.

DISCUSSION

The discussion is accordance with the objectives and hypotheses of the study

to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on ICDS Programme among mothers of under-five children.

Demographic variables: Majority of the female adults were in the age group of 20-30 years, 86.66% of the respondents found to be married, 50% of the respondents educational status was 6-10thstd, 66.66% of the respondents belongs to Hindu religion and 33.33% from Muslim, Majority 56.66% of the respondents were nuclear family background, Majority 83.33% of female adult monthly income is below Rs.15,000/, 76.66% of the respondents does not have the previous knowledge on ICDS programme, 13.33% of the respondents' source of information is mass media

In the present study Pretest knowledge score was inadequate 86.66% (>50 %), Moderate 13.34% (<50 %) and Adequate was 0.0% (>75 %).

But in post test 63.0% of them had moderate knowledge (51-75 %), 36.67% of them had adequate knowledge (< 50 %) and none of them had inadequate knowledge (≤50 %).

The present study revealed that there is lack of appropriate information on ICDS programme among mothers of under five children Thus Structured Teaching Programme was conducted.

According to stated hypothesis (H1) the overall mean knowledge in pretest was found to be 33.5% and mean knowledge in post test was 72.3%, the mean knowledge enhancement was found to be 38.8%. Hence, the stated hypothesis H₁ is accepted because there was a significant (5% level) improvement in knowledge scores of mothers of under five children after

administration of the structured teaching programme.

CONCLUSION

The findings of final study revealed that there was a significant gain in knowledge scores of the mothers of under-five children after the session of STP at 0.05 level. The study concluded that STP had a great potential for accelerating the awareness regarding ICDS programme.

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